

IMPACT OF EFFECTUAL PROPENSITY ON ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

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Abstract

For decades, entrepreneurship has been promoted in academia and tourism sector and has it been seen as an opportunity for new business ventures. In terms of entrepreneurial behavior, effectual logic shows how the individual uses his or her resources to create new opportunities. In this context, this paper aims to determine effectual propensity as an antecedent of entrepreneurial intentions. For this purpose, and based on the TPB model, we conducted our research with tourism students from Cadiz and Seville (Spain) universities with Smart PLS 3. The results show that effectual propensity influences entrepreneurial intentions and that attitude and perceived behavioral control mediate between subjective norms and intentions. Our research has a great added value since we have studied for the first time efficacious propensity as an antecedent of intentions in people who have never been entrepreneurs.

Keywords: TPB, entrepreneurial intentions, effectual propensity, tourism students, SEM.

1. Introduction

The academic literature highlights the importance of entrepreneurial intention as a precursor to entrepreneurial decision making (Maheshwari, 2021). Fostering entrepreneurship is crucial in all countries, as it contributes to the development of the economy by increasing productivity, creating new employment opportunities, and revitalizing markets through the development of new products (Esfandiar et al., 2019). In particular, the tourism sector offers many entrepreneurship and business development opportunities. This industry promotes economic development in its geographical area of influence, as it acts as an engine for other economic sectors. In this context, the tourism entrepreneur is key to developing attractive destinations, creating employment, and increasing labor productivity and income of the local population. (Tleuberdinova et al., 2021)

In the initial stages of the entrepreneurial process, the decision to entrepreneurship is preceded by the detection of opportunities and the intention of creating a new venture (Liñán, 2008). The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen et al., 1991) proposes a helpful model for analyzing entrepreneurial intention. (Krueger et al., 2000; Liñán, 2004; Soomro et al., 2018; Urban & Ratsimanetrimanana, 2019). Applying TPB concepts, entrepreneurial intention depends on the personal attitude (PA), subjective norms (SN) and perceived behavioral control (PBC) of the

potential entrepreneur. In another sense, and according to Sarasvathy (2001), the entrepreneur may apply a causal or effectual logic while creating his or her new business. To date, scholars have analyzed the effectual versus causal logic by studying the behavior of individuals who have already created companies (Brettel et al., 2012; Guo et al., 2016; Schmidt & Heidenreich, 2014). However, efficacy research does not analyze entrepreneurial intention. (Shahidi, 2020). The literature has not studied the individual propensity toward one or the other logic in the case of the potential entrepreneur, the one who intends to become an entrepreneur but has not yet done so. The theories of entrepreneurship concerning the study of entrepreneurial intention seemed incompatible with the theories on the type of entrepreneurial behavior to develop since they apply to two different moments of the entrepreneurial process. Considering this gap, the study of the propensity for effectual or causal behavior prior to the firm's creation would add value to entrepreneurship research. (Martín-Navarro et al., 2021). Based on the above, the aim of this paper is to test the direct and indirect impact of the effectual propensity of potential entrepreneurs on their entrepreneurial intention.

The literature on entrepreneurship widely recognizes the university's role as a pool of entrepreneurs. (Lechuga Sancho et al., 2021). The reasons why students do or do not intend to run their own business have been the subject of interest in the entrepreneurship literature (Trang & Doanh, 2019). Because the tourism sector offers many opportunities for entrepreneurial development, our study was conducted among the University of Cadiz and the University of Seville tourism students. Exploring the entrepreneurial intentions of this type of student is crucial for the current and future development of the tourism and hospitality industry. (Tsai et al., 2016).

The impact of effectual propensity on entrepreneurial intention modeled according to the TPB was analyzed to achieve the objective. Hypothesis testing revealed that seven hypotheses were statistically significant, and two were rejected. Expressly, it was rejected that SNs directly impact entrepreneurial intentions and perceived behavioral control. However, the effectual propensity of the potential entrepreneur did show a direct, even slightly, effect on intentions and indirect effects through PA and PBC.

2. Background and Research Hypothesis

The literature on entrepreneurship provides adequate justification for the relationships to test in this study. The following is a brief description of the basic concepts related to effectual behavior and TPB application to entrepreneurial intention models. Those concepts will subsequently allow us to justify and establish the hypotheses to test to respond to our research objective.

2.1. Effectuation

Decisions on how to develop a business idea, acquire the necessary resources and implement effective decision making occur under conditions of uncertainty (Villani et al., 2018). For a long time, entrepreneurship researchers have assumed that individuals pursuing entrepreneurial opportunities are guided solely by rational, goal-directed behavior (Perry et al., 2012). This thinking fits into a causal behavioral model of entrepreneurship (Sarasvathy, 2001). In contrast, the effectual behavior theory of entrepreneurship proposes a different approach to explain how some entrepreneurs make decisions (Sarasvathy, 2001). Thus, causation and effectuation represent two distinct frameworks applicable to new venture creation. The first is characterized by careful planning, while the latter is based on a more flexible, adaptive and experimental strategy. (Read & Sarasvathy, 2005).

Focusing on the above framework, the logic of effectuation is that entrepreneurs use a set of means already given to them and focus on deciding what they can create with them (Sarasvathy, 2001). When creating new ventures, entrepreneurs who follow an effectual approach, as they make decisions and observe the results of those decisions, use this new information to change course.

Thus, entrepreneurs who follow an effectual logic are less likely to plan for the future and prefer to change their initial goals and vision for their new venture. Thus, instead of predicting the future, they are more likely to work with the means they have under their control and make the necessary adjustments. (Dew et al., 2009).

For Sarasvathy (2001), this approach offers five decision-making principles (means, association, affordable loss, contingencies, and control): (1) start with the *means* (entrepreneur's skills, knowledge and social relationships), wherein the process of creating a new venture, goals emerge based on the entrepreneur's available *means*; (2) form partnerships to seek business opportunities together, share resources and work together, with less uncertainty and more control of each partner's business; (3) focusing on downside risk, and worrying more about the *affordable loss* than the profits to achieve; (4) taking advantage of contingencies and not thinking of these contingencies as obstacles, but as new opportunities to exploit; and, (5) controlling the future, which is uncertain but controllable because entrepreneurs can influence trends, create new markets and face new challenges.

To understand the behavior of this type of individual, we must determine their orientation towards effectual principles. Sarasvathy's (2001) theory has been widely studied by the academic community as applied to entrepreneurs starting new ventures (Burmeister-lamp, 2016; Chandler et al., 2011; Matalamäki et al., 2017). However, few have been concerned with the effectual orientation of potential entrepreneurs. In this regard, Martín-Navarro et al. (2021) are the first to use the concept of effectual propensity (EP). The EP determines the orientation of a person towards an effectual logic before starting a business.

2.2. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Entrepreneurial intention has become a fascinating field in entrepreneurship research. It becomes a way to find out the desire and commitment of people to create new ventures. Entrepreneurship research shows those personal and contextual factors that motivate the individual to start an entrepreneurial project (Shahzad et al., 2021). To this end, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), an accepted model for analyzing the propensity of individuals to develop particular behavior, helps study entrepreneurial intention. (Krueger et al., 2000). According to the TPB model, intentions are shown to be the result of three factors: (1) personal attitude (PA) toward a given behavior, (2) subjective norms (SN) determined by social pressure and, (3) perceived behavioral control (PBC) understood as the ability to carry out a specific behavior. (Ajzen, 1991). This theory has been widely used in entrepreneurship and has been empirically tested by numerous scholars. (Liñan, 2004; Soomro et al., 2018; Urban & Ratsimanetrimanana, 2019). In this sense, the literature on entrepreneurship adapts the general elements of the TPB to the explanation of entrepreneurial intention. Thus, PA toward behavior refers to how individuals have a positive or negative personal appraisal of being an entrepreneur. Individuals' attraction toward the desire to start their own business affects their entrepreneurial intention. (Ajzen, 1991). SN reflects the pressure individuals receive from their social environment to perform certain behaviors. (Ajzen, 1991). In an entrepreneurial setting, SN refers to the importance that individuals attach to the approval of their closest circle (family, friends or other people of reference) to their decision to start a business. (Liñan, 2008). Finally, PBC refers to the perception that individuals have that entrepreneurship is easy or difficult and can control this behavior. (Ajzen, 2002).

2.3. Research model

Attitudes are psychological traits that influence entrepreneurial intentions. Attitudes can change over time and be influenced by education or experience. Underlying attitudes are cognitive structures. (Krueger, 2007). The cognitive structure is the set of [ideas](#) that an individual has about

a given area of knowledge and how he or she organizes them in his or her mind. We can point to effectual logic among the cognitive structures, including decision-making and problem-solving methods. (Sarasvathy & Dew, 2008). Thus, an individual's EP can be a precedent for PA and can be raised:

H1: PE is positively related to PA toward entrepreneurship.

According to Yoon & Cho (2021), an internal locus of control is positively related to effectual and causal behavior. However, the central theme of the entrepreneur's effectual logic is control and not prediction, which is characteristic of causal behavior. (Sarasvathy, 2001). Effectual behavior considers that individuals perceive that they can control their future. Even though the future is uncertain, effectual entrepreneurs perceive creating new markets and opportunities. (Sarasvathy, 2001). This idea is a perception of having the ability to control events. Therefore, control as an effectual principle is connected to the TPB concept of PBC, understood as the perception that one can carry out a particular behavior. (Ajzen, 1991). For this reason, it can be argued that:

H2: PE is positively related to PBC.

As discussed, according to efficacy, effectual behavior relies on five principles: means, partnership, affordable loss, contingencies, and control orientation. Traditionally, the entrepreneurship literature analyzes effectual behavior following the creation or development of a firm. Following Martín-Navarro et al. (2021), we will apply these same principles to the effectual propensity of individuals, i.e., the tendency to develop effectual behavior before creating the firm. A review of previous literature allows us to relate the principles of effectual behavior and the analogy of the propensity towards effectual behavior to entrepreneurial intention. Thus, as part of his or her means, knowledge and skills of the potential entrepreneur have a positive effect on entrepreneurial intention (Liñan, 2004). Similarly, risk propensity, which we can relate to *affordable loss*, also influences entrepreneurial intention. (Shahzad et al., 2021). Concerning the effectual principle of *partnership*, there is evidence of how collective entrepreneurship explains entrepreneurial intention among rural youth members of agricultural cooperatives. (Bouichou et al., 2021). Along the same lines, there is also evidence that team cooperation moderates the positive relationship between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention. (Li & Wu, 2019). As the ability to recognize opportunities in difficult situations, contingency can also be related to intentions. Thus, Al Mamun et al. (2016) found that students who could identify opportunities increased entrepreneurial intentions. Finally, environmental *control* orientation is closely related to the internal locus of control concept. (Somi, 2015). This concept assumes that the individual has control over his or her destiny and thinks that what happens depends on his or her abilities and knowledge. (Mueller & Thomas, 2001). Therefore, if the entrepreneur feels strong in controlling the destiny, he or she will be more confident about the chances of success, thus increasing his or her entrepreneurial intentions. In this sense, many scholars have found the effect of internal locus of control on entrepreneurial intentions. (Annisa et al., 2021; Erickson & Laing, 2016; Nasip et al., 2017; Torres et al., 2017). Given that EP is governed by the same principles as effectual behavior after entrepreneurship (Martín-Navarro et al., 2021), we can affirm that there must also be a relationship between PE and EI. There is empirical evidence for this relationship. In a sample of graduates from a leading business school in Pakistan, it was found that training students in the effectual entrepreneurial logic significantly increased their intentions to start a business. (Qureshi & Mahdi, 2014). Based on the above, we can argue that:

H3: PE is positively related to entrepreneurial intention.

On the other hand, SN involves a significant social influence on individuals. When individuals are in a group, they feel that they must have appropriate behavior, usually conditioned by family,

friends or peers (Yasa et al., 2021). In this way, SN presents a significant relationship with the individual's attitude (Kotler & Keller, 2015). Piroth et al. (2020) found empirical evidence for the positive effect of SN on PA in a study on online grocery shoppers. Similarly, Yasa et al. (2021) tested how SN had a positive impact on PA wearing a face mask. These arguments allow the following hypothesis:

H4: SN is positively related to PA toward entrepreneurship.

The support of the most influential people who make up the SN of individuals and influence their PA, as discussed, also influences the behavior of those individuals. Thus, individuals' behavior is favorable to entrepreneurship when potential entrepreneurs have the emotional support of those important people in their lives (Ramos-Rodríguez et al., 2019). In this sense, a study in a sample of Italian university students found that the effect of SN on PBC was significant and that it was more robust in the female group than in the male group. (Scafarto et al., 2019). Eysel & Vatansver Durmaz (2019) also found a positive relationship between SN on TPB in undergraduate social sciences students and natural sciences studying at Bahçeşehir University. Moreover, although only partially, a relationship between SN and PBC was also found in a study in a sample of international students at universities throughout Turkey (Usman & Yennita, 2019). This previous evidence justifies to propose the following hypothesis :

H5: SN is positively related to PBC.

Regarding the influence of PA on PBC, Usman & Yennita (2019) found a strong effect of PA on PBC in college students. Similarly, in a sample of high school students in Portugal, the relationship of PA on PBC was found to be significant (Do Paço et al., 2011). Furthermore, in a study among farmers that analyzed the factors affecting the intention to continue with Conservation Agriculture during 2020, Tama et al. (2021) found scientific evidence of PA's relationship with PBC. These arguments allow formulating the following research hypothesis:

H7: PA toward entrepreneurship is positively related to PBC.

As reflected in the entrepreneurship literature within the TPB framework, PA, SN, and PBC are determinants of entrepreneurial intention. (Krueger et al., 2000; Liñan, 2004; Soomro et al., 2018; Urban & Ratsimanetrimanana, 2019). In this sense, PA is the determinant that motivates intentions in more studies. However, the relationship between SN and intentions is the one that is most often not supported. Of the three factors, the one that usually has the most significant relationship with intentions is PBC, while SN usually has the weakest impact. (Lortie & Castogiovanni, 2015). Nevertheless, we have found sufficient empirical evidence that PA, SN and PBC are antecedents of entrepreneurial intentions. Thus, Kautonen et al. (2011) found a positive relationship of the three factors on entrepreneurial intentions in their study of the working-age population in Finland. Similarly, in an investigation in a sample of students at a university in Yemen, the three predictors of TPB intention were found to be significant (Al-Jubari, 2019). In addition, in the analysis of data obtained through a questionnaire answered by Information System students, it was also found that the three variables that precede intentions in the TPB impact the students' intention to create a new business. (Kaltenecker et al., 2015). Based on the arguments presented, we propose the following relationships:

H6: SN is positively related to entrepreneurial intention.

H8: PA toward entrepreneurship is positively related to entrepreneurial intention.

H9: PBC is positively related to entrepreneurial intention.

Figure 1 shows the relationships considered in the hypotheses we have put forward.

Figure 1. Research model

3. Methodology

3.1. Data collection

The tourism degree students, who voluntarily participated in the research, were interviewed using a self-administered questionnaire using non-probabilistic sampling. Experts and researchers reviewed the questionnaire for content validity and included a pilot test among 30 students. The questions were formulated using a 7-point Likert scale, where one means strongly disagree, and seven means strongly agree. After data collection, we obtained a sample of 464 correctly completed questionnaires.

Of the sample, 56.71% are students from the University of Seville, while 43.29% are from Cadiz. Concerning the sample, 71.02% of the respondents are women compared to 28.98% men. Between 18 and 21 years old are 56.04% of the cases, 37.58% are between 22 and 25 years old, and the rest are older than 25 years old; most of them are Spanish, only 2.6% are foreigners; 31.82% of those surveyed belong to a family whose parents have had or have their own business. Moreover, 34.20% have worked or are currently working, compared to 46.84% who have never worked. The rest have worked, are currently working, or are self-employed or work both for themselves and others.

3.2. Measurement scales

According to Sarasvathy (2001) y Gabrielsson & Politis (2011), the effectual orientation is measured independently of the causal orientation. This research focuses on the effectual orientation employing the EP construct. Therefore, we determined the scale with the indicators or items necessary to measure this variable, which is not directly observable by the researcher. The indicators of the EP construct were adapted from the work of Martín-Navarro et al. (2021) and are integrated into five subdimensions: (1) means orientation which is measured through three items, (2) association orientation was measured through four (3) affordable loss orientation is composed of three indicators (4) contingency orientation of four and, (5) control orientation has been measured with four items. To measure the constructs of the Theory of Planned Behavior

(PA, PBC, SN and EI), we used an adapted version of the Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire (EIQ) (Liñán et al., 2011). Thus, the four variables belonging to the TPB were measured with the following number of items: (1) PA with five indicators, (2) PBC likewise with five items, (3) SN was measured with four indicators and, (4) EI with six. As proposed by the authors, to avoid the problems of response set bias and the halo effect, the items were randomly mixed and ordered in the questionnaire.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Analysis of the measurement model

PLS-SEM allows the estimation of complex models with many constructs, indicator variables, and structural trajectories without imposing distributional assumptions on the data (Roldán & Sánchez-Franco, 2012). PLS is a recommended method for studying latent construct models made up of composite (Rigdon, 2016). For the model analysis, we have used the SmartPLS 3 (Ringle et al., 2015) software, which allows us to analyze the relationships between latent variables and their indicators, i.e., how these constructs measure their respective indicators. Likewise, PLS evaluates the measurement of the variables based on individual reliability, construct reliability, discriminant validity and convergent validity. Reliability ensures that the measurement produces consistent results, and validity ensures that the indicators of a construct measure the construct they are intended to measure and not another.

The reliability of individual items must be satisfied that the loadings are greater than 0.707 (Carmines & Zeller, 1979). As Table 1 shows, only the means orientation (MO) in the EP has a lower loading and will be eliminated from the analysis. Subsequently, the reliability of the construct is analyzed through Dijkstra-Henseler rho_A in all cases with values higher than 0.7. (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015). The composite reliability (Werts et al., 1974) should be higher than 0.8, as Nunnally & Bernstein (1995) suggested. To complete this analysis, convergent validity is checked through the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). In this case, the values must be greater than 0.5 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), and this is the case.

Table 1. Reliability and convergent validity

Construct/Indicator	Loads	rho_A	Compound reliability	AVE
Effectual propensity (EP)		0.766	0.831	0.554
Media orientation	0.642			
Guidance to the association	0.742			
Contingency orientation	0.821			
Control orientation	0.760			
Personal Attitude (PA)		0.922	0.938	0.751
Being an entrepreneur has more advantages than disadvantages for me.	0.815			
A career in business is attractive to me	0.906			
If I had the opportunity and the resources, I would like to start a company.	0.856			
Being an entrepreneur would bring me great satisfaction.	0.863			
Among several options, I would prefer to be an entrepreneur	0.891			
Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC)		0.912	0.935	0.741
Starting a business and keeping it running would be easy for me.	0.820			
I am ready to create a viable business	0.897			
I can control the process of setting up a new company.	0.895			
I know how to develop a business project	0.861			
If I tried to start a company, I would have a good chance of success.	0.828			
Subjective norms (SN)		0.872	0.921	0.796
If you decided to start a business, would your immediate family approve of that decision?	0.879			
If you decided to start a company, would your friends approve of that decision?	0.918			
If you decided to start a company, would your peers approve of that decision?	0.879			

Entrepreneurial Intention (EI)	0.958	0.966	0.827
I am willing to do anything to be an entrepreneur.	0.851		
My career goal is to become an entrepreneur	0.931		
I will do my best to start and run my own company.	0.918		
I am determined to start a company in the future	0.936		
I have been thinking very seriously about starting a company	0.903		
I have the firm intention of creating a company someday.	0.913		

Table 2 shows the discriminant validity analysis using the heterotraitmonotrait (HTMT) relationship. (Henseler et al., 2016). This ratio must have values below 0.85 (Gold et al., 2001) to ensure that discriminant validity is satisfied, as can be verified.

Table 2. Discriminant validity (HTMT)

	EN	PC	EO	EN	SN
EN					
PBC	0,560				
EP	0,448	0,407			
EI	0,805	0,641	0,441		
SN	0,415	0,332	0,444	0,370	

In the second-order construct, the EP, in the first step, eliminated the dimension "affordable loss orientation" because the loads are lower than 0.707. In this second step, the dimension "means orientation" is eliminated for the same reason. Once the measurement model has been refined, we continue with the analysis of the structural model.

4.2. Structural model

After analyzing the reliability and validity, the structural model should be evaluated to identify the relationships between the constructs of the proposed research model (Velicia Martín et al., 2020). This analysis tests whether the hypotheses and the relationships of the constructs of the theoretical model are supported (Henseler et al., 2015). The evaluation of the structural model involves the estimation of the path loadings and the values of R^2 . For this purpose, a bootstrapping technique with 5,000 resamples is used to test the proposed hypotheses (Hair et al., 2011).

The path loadings indicate the strength of the relationships between the explanatory variables and the variables to be explained (Ramírez-Correa et al., 2019). The results of the path loadings are shown in Table 3. In this sense, it is found that out of the nine relationships proposed in the theoretical model, seven of them are significant. The unsupported hypotheses are H5 and H6. Therefore, the relationship SN on PBC is not significant, nor SN on EI.

Table 3. Results of significance tests of the coefficients of the structural model.

Hypothesis	β (Standard Path Coeff.)	T Statistics	P Values	CI	Sig	
H1: EP→AT	0,279	6,489	0,000	(0,198;0,365)	Yes	***
H2: EP→PBC	0,175	3,90	0,000	(0,085;0,262)	Yes	***
H3: EP→IN	0,077	2,407	0,016	(0,015;0,138)	Yes	**
H4: SN→AT	0,277	5,297	0,000	(0,171;0,379)	Yes	***
H5: SN →PBC	0,084	1,861	0,063	(-0,006;0,171)	No	n.s.
H6: SN →EI	0,016	0,534	0,593	(-0,043;0,075)	No	n.s.
H7: AT→PBC	0,425	10,345	0,000	(0,344;0,504)	Yes	***
H8: AT→EI	0,587	18,552	0,000	(0,523;0,647)	Yes	***
H9: PBC→ EI	0,264	7,382	0,000	(0,193;0,333)	Yes	***

Note: Significant at $p^{***} < 0.001$, $p^{**} < 0.05$

R² values measure the predictive power of structural models. Interpreted as multiple regression results, the R² indicates the variance explained by the exogenous variables (Ramírez-Correa et al., 2019). R² values are shown in Table 4. Hair et al. (2014) R² values above 0.67 are considered high, between 0.67 and 0.33 moderate, between 0.33 and 0.19 weak and values below 0.19 are unacceptable. In our case, Entrepreneurial Intention presents a moderate R², while the values for PA and PBC are weak.

Table 4. R²-values

	R ²	R ² adjusted
Personal Attitude	0.206	0.202
Perceived behavioral control	0.310	0.305
Entrepreneurial intention	0.640	0.637

The global model fit is performed using the values of the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR). A value of 0 would represent a perfect fit, although values below 0.08 present a good fit (Henseler et al., 2014). In our model, SRMR presents a value of 0.052 lower than the reference value, so our model presents a good fit.

As for indirect effects, there are some significant ones among the model constructs (see Table 5). In addition to showing a direct and positive relationship with EI, EP shows significant indirect effects through PA and PBC. Despite not showing a significant direct relationship with EI or PBC, SN shows a significant indirect relationship through PA with EI and PBC variables.

Table 5. Indirect effects

Specific indirect effects	Route (β)	Statistics T	p-value	CI
EP -> AT -> IN	0.164	6.204	0.000	(0.110.0.216)
EP -> PBC -> IN	0.046	3.342	0.001	(0.022.0.077)
EP -> AT -> PBC -> IN	0.031	4.506	0.000	(0.019.0.046)
EP -> AT -> PBC	0.118	6.051	0.000	(0.081.0.157)
AT -> PBC -> IN	0.112	5.817	0.000	(0.077.0.152)
SN -> AT -> IN	0.162	4.973	0.000	(0.100.0.228)
SN -> PBC -> IN	0.022	1.846	0.065	(0.000.0.048)
SN -> AT -> PBC -> IN	0.031	3.759	0.000	(0.017.0.050)
SN -> AT -> PBC	0.118	4.475	0.000	(0.071.0.174)

Importance-performance matrix analysis (IPMA) is carried out (see Table 6 and Figure 2). The IPMA assists the PLS-SEM results through a four-quadrant diagram depicted in Figure 2. The vertical axis represents attribute performance, from poor performance to good performance. The horizontal axis represents the perceived importance of the attributes from unimportant to very important. (García-Fernández et al., 2020).

Table 6. IPMA (Business Intention)

	Total effect (importance)	Index value (yield)
Effectual propensity	0.711	63.127
Personal Attitude	0.859	66.411
Perceived behavioral control	0.331	45.520

Social norm	0.312	75.353
Mean	0.553	62.603

The quadrants are delimited using the mean performance and mean importance listed in the PEI results table. As shown in figure 2, the third quadrant is SN, the variable with the highest importance, but it contributes the least to the EI effect, as does PBC, which is in the fourth quadrant. The variable with the most significant contribution to the total effect is PA, followed by EP.

Figure 2. IPMA (Business Intention)

Finally, the model's predictive power is analyzed, which allows testing the model's generalizability to other populations. We apply a PLSpredict, an out-of-sample approach developed. (Shmueli et al., 2016). Following Roldan & Cepeda (2017) with the PLSpredictive technique, we obtained results expressed through the variables RMSE (R Mean Square Error) and MAE (Mean Absolute Error) and $Q_{\text{prediction}}^2$. For the model to have predictive power, the value of Q^2 must be greater than zero. In our case, all the values in the last column are positive (see table 7). Similarly, we obtained positive values for RMSE and MAE, showing good predictability. (Woodside, 2013). Therefore, this research demonstrated the predictive validity, or out-of-sample predictability, of the proposed model to predict the values of new cases.

Table 7. Evaluation of PLS predictions

	RMSE	MAE	$Q_{\text{prediction}}^2$
Attitude	0.901	0.710	0.196
Perceived behavioral control	0.922	0.757	0.156
Entrepreneurial intention	0.901	0.749	0.195

5. DISCUSSION

The academic literature has studied effectuation logic during the entrepreneurial process. That is, effectuation theory has analyzed the behavior of entrepreneurs who have already started their businesses. However, this behavior has not been analyzed in people who have not started a business and are in an early stage. This research integrates the entrepreneurial intention model with the effectual logic. For this purpose, an extended TPB model with the Effectual Propensity variable has been developed. The extended TPB model with EP can be considered a valuable

model for predicting entrepreneurial intention in tourism. As shown, the theoretical model has satisfactory psychometric qualities. In addition, the TPB model has increased its predictive power with the EP variable.

In this paper, it was found in a sample of university students that PE is a determinant of EI, both directly and indirectly through PA and PBC. Similarly, it is confirmed that both PA and PBC present a direct and positive relationship with entrepreneurial intention in the sample analyzed. These findings are in line with the results of many other authors in the area of entrepreneurship (Krueger et al., 2000; Liñan, 2004; Soomro et al., 2018; Urban & Ratsimanetrimanana, 2019). Furthermore, even with those of Ahamed & Limbu (2018) in their study of the intention to use credit cards. PE presents a positive and direct relationship with EI and significant indirect effects with the variables PA and PBC that contribute to explaining entrepreneurial intention. The direct relationship between SN and EI shows a non-significant relationship. The same occurs in other studies, such as that of Doanh & Bernat (2019), which did not find the effect of SN on EI among university students in Vietnam. However, it is in contrast to other studies that have found this relationship significant in students' entrepreneurial intentions. (Al-Jubari, 2019; Ridha & Wahyu, 2017). On the other hand, the indirect effect of SN through PA is significant on both EI and PBC.

It should also be noted that the IPMA analysis shows that attitude is the exogenous variable that contributes most to the total effect of the endogenous variable EI, followed by EP. In contrast, the variable that contributes least to the total effect is PBC. The theoretical model analyzed with a sample of students of the Degree in Tourism presents adequate predictive power. The results obtained in our analysis can be generalized to other samples.

6. CONCLUSIONS

There is great interest in understanding the antecedents of the intention to create new companies among academics who study entrepreneurship. Among others, the TPB model stands out as one of the most used by researchers to achieve this goal. In this sense, our research has carried out empirical work. The effectual propensity is proposed as an antecedent of entrepreneurial intentions, together with the rest of the TPB determinants (PA, SN and PBC). Our study has a great added value since we have not found in the literature any study that analyzes EP intentions in people who have not yet become entrepreneurs. The results of the hypothesis testing show two critical findings. First, and as the most important finding, this study has shown that EP influences EI. Moreover second, PE also affects EI indirectly through PA and PBC.

Overall, our work contributes to investigating entrepreneurial intentions by providing a new determinant not previously investigated on EI. Thus, we have shown that EI affects students' intentions towards creating a new venture. Similarly, our work has social implications. Our results differentiate between higher education students' effectual and causal orientation. It will allow adjusting the curricula to contain more personalized training in entrepreneurship and strengthen the effectual orientation of students who require it. In this way, public policies must encourage entrepreneurs in the initial stages of the entrepreneurial process. From the business point of view, our research allows us to determine the orientation shown by professionals in the business world to evaluate the PE of their employees, managers, and even business partners. Both those with whom entrepreneurs already have a relationship and those who require a prior evaluation of their entrepreneurial orientation before assuming future commitments. In this same sense, how the university emits knowledge to the market is through hiring its students. For this reason, it is interesting to differentiate between the orientations of these individuals with entrepreneurial intentions. Thus, the labor market will differentiate, according to its needs, the competencies, behaviors or orientations of the graduates it hires.

This research should be interpreted with some limitations in mind. Because the findings have been the results of a single study, and with students from two geographically close universities,

they should not be generalized. It would be advisable to repeat this study in different samples with different educational and cultural contexts and socio-demographic profiles. Nevertheless, these limitations present opportunities for future lines of research. For example, it would be interesting to test these scales in other samples from other countries or cultures. Furthermore, even to consider PE as a moderating variable in other models of entrepreneurial intentions.

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